

SWOT-ANALYSIS OF SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF ANDIZHAN REGION

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Abstract: The method of SWOT-analysis is effective in the analysis of socio-economic development of regions. The article describes the state of socio-economic development of Andijan region using the method of SWOT-analysis.

Keywords: Territory, socio-economic development, SWOT analysis, natural resources, tourism, infrastructure, population growth.

Andijan region has borders with the Kyrgyz Republic in the north-east and south, Fergana region in the west and Namangan region in the north-west.

The region has cities that are subordinated to 2 regions and 9 districts, 14 districts, 78 settlements, 882 mahallas, 455 settlements.

The climate is sharply continental, dry.

The weather is relatively mild in winter, as the mountain ranges block the inflow of cold air into the Fergana Valley. Summers are hot, the average temperature in July is 27 ° C, winters are relatively cold, the average temperature in January is -3 ° C. The vegetation period is 217 days, the average annual rainfall is 200-250 mm. Wild animals are rare, there are reptiles, rodents, birds, fish in ponds.

The regional center is Andijan, the largest city is in the Fergana Valley, and the third largest city in the Republic of Uzbekistan after Tashkent and Samarkand. The city is located at an altitude of 450 meters above sea level, along the banks of the Andijan River.

Andijan region is richer in water resources than other regions of Uzbekistan, it receives water from rivers, mountains, perennial snow and glaciers. The main river is Qoradarya (one of the tributaries of the Syrdarya), its tributaries are Maylisuv, Akbori, Aravonsay and others. Gravel and sand from this river are widely used in construction works in the region.

There are 2.8 thousand hectares of undeveloped agricultural lands, 21.0 thousand hectares of pastures and 1.0 thousand hectares of reclamation lands in the region, a total of 24.8 thousand hectares of lands, hills and pastures. In the future, the cultivation of these lands, the installation of pumping stations and gardens in the hills will significantly contribute to the development of agriculture.

Oil and gas make up the bulk of the region's mineral.

There are reserves of 26.2 million cubic meters of sand and gravel, 51.9 million cubic meters of building stone.

Strengths of Andijan region (S):

- high proportion of abled population, especially young people under 30 years of age;
- relatively high capacity and level of personnel knowledge, resourceful, diligent, innovative workforce;
- Favorable natural and climatic conditions, relatively high land productivity;
- Favorable geographical location of the region for trade development;
- Favorable climate and conditions for recreation in the future for the development of tourism and excursion services;
- high-tech industry - the dominance of engineering in the regional system of industrial production;
- high level of craft development;
- mechanical engineering, light and large high investment attractiveness and large size of opportunities;
- richness of roads and railways;
- Favorable geographical conditions for transit and transportation of domestic products to other countries.

Weaknesses of Andijan region (W):

- high rates of population growth in high-density confined space;
- relatively low level of solvency of the population;
- high share of the informal employment sector;
- low value-added industries, especially high levels of employment in agriculture;
- high depreciation of fixed assets, the process of modernization and technical armament, especially in the chemical and food industries;
- Low level of industrial capacity commissioning
- Low level of vegetable and fruit processing
- inefficient use of available mineral resources;
- Insufficient development of the business environment to stimulate investment activity, weak participation of financial institutions in the implementation of investment projects;

- Limited opportunities for efficient use of the railway network and highways;
- Low level of access to information services.

Opportunities of Andijan region (O):

- achieving optimal rates of population growth;
- Increasing the mobilization and entrepreneurship of training institutions,
- the development of educational and scientific, educational and innovative capabilities;
- Modernization of infrastructure (gas, water, heat and electricity supply);
- Development of high value-added sectors of the economy in order to increase incomes, increase employment in the labor-intensive sectors of production;
- creation of jobs for the region in the field of traditional crafts, including family business;
- Development of fruit and vegetable processing through the use of modern technologies and techniques;
- Development of animal husbandry, fisheries, beekeeping and poultry;
- Development of "regional growth points" in the engineering, chemical, light and food industries. increase the competitiveness of products of regional producers through the use of high technology and innovation;
- Development of the construction materials industry based on the efficient use of local raw materials;
- Development of market services (microfinance, leasing, insurance, consulting, marketing, etc.), tourism and leisure services, information and communication services in the future;
- Attracting investments in tourism development. The opportunities for the rapid development of ecotourism in our region are high. Ecotourism refers to the
- interaction of nature conservation, ecology, biology, geology, geography, botany, and other natural sciences through nature [5].

Expected threats to the future socio-economic development of Andijan region(T):

- Exacerbation of social problems in rural and densely populated areas due to insufficient availability of jobs, social services and infrastructure;
- Increased dependence on water resources in neighboring countries;

- the risk of deterioration of the ecological situation as a result of the preservation of soil salinity, the presence of reclamation lands;
- Loss of competitiveness of agriculture, especially fruit and vegetable products in foreign markets due to the problem of transportation of goods;
- Depreciation of fixed assets, technical and technological backwardness of some industries lead to the exclusion of regional products from domestic and regional markets by producers of goods from neighboring regions and foreign countries;
- In the environment of growing demand, the low level of processing of agricultural products and the complete absence of storage and packaging conditions can lead to the loss of export opportunities;
- The fact that the bulk of investments are directed to the non-manufacturing sector can have a negative impact on the development of the real sector of the;
- economy and lead to macroeconomic imbalances;
- Risk of transport network disruption in winter.

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